

Research Brief

Research Brief: population, setting, key findings to advance the study of health disparities.

EVAL adds new publications to the website "Publications" dashboard and sends citations to COMMS and ERC.

ERC identifies the project and adds to ERC Resource list.

Comms sends them to CHER for vetting. They send analysis to COMMS.

2 weeks

ERC reaches out to project PI through EIT (through Asana form EIT request) to make sure they don't already have a lay summary.

Requests logos and social media handles of project institution and community partners and add to the Box folder.

COMMS creates Box folder/Asana project for papers given the green light. Taps ERC.

2 weeks

COMMS (MED WRITING) writes research brief.

CCPH edits for plain, concise language.

6 weeks

ERC sends draft of summary to project PI for approval and/or additional edits and submits approved brief to COMMS.

COMMS runs through translation, design, 508 compliance

5 weeks

- Translation Vendor
- CDCC Language Corps
- 508 Compliance Vendor

COMMS adds to editorial calendar for immediate dissemination on the website, newsletter and social media.

2 weeks

ERC sends final link to project PI.

COMMS collects analytics on downloads.

Updated 9/23/2022